

Amidst the COVID-19 Pandemic: Factors Affecting Teacher's Job Satisfaction in Public Secondary School

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Abstract

The motivation of educators is an essential component in fostering excellence in both teaching and learning. Motivated educators are more likely to encourage their students to study while in the classroom, to assure the implementation of educational innovations, and to have feelings of pleasure and satisfaction in their own lives. Further, this study investigates the factors affecting the teacher's job satisfaction in public secondary school, specifically: (1) the satisfaction and dissatisfaction levels of teachers; and (2) the significant difference in the teachers' levels of satisfaction when grouped according to sex, age, educational attainment, academic discipline. Based on the statistical analysis of data, there was no significant difference in the level of satisfaction when teachers were grouped according to sex, age, educational attainment, and academic discipline.

Keywords: Job Satisfaction, Teachers' Motivation, Public School Teachers, Descriptive Study, COVID-19 Pandemic

Introduction

The relevance of job satisfaction among employees of companies and institutions dates back to the second part of the twentieth century, with the publication of Maslow's hierarchy of needs theory (1956). Since then, experts have addressed the issue and conducted many analytical investigations. The trend toward human interactions shines greater attention on the importance of morale and improving working conditions for employees of enterprises and institutions trying to increase productivity. According to Conley et al. (1989), employee job satisfaction is a major component of the work environment and one of the primary determinants defining organizational climate in every firm. Furthermore, Hoy and Misked (1987) noted that work satisfaction is a critical aspect of an organization's overall effectiveness.

Teacher motivation is critical in promoting excellence in teaching and learning. Motivated teachers are more likely to urge their pupils to study in the classroom, to ensure the implementation of educational changes, and experience emotions of pleasure and fulfillment.

Teacher motivation is a significant predictor of student achievement in the classroom. Gullatt and Bennet (1995) suggested that in today's technology culture experiencing fundamental changes, the requirement for motivated instructors has reached crisis proportions. They say that motivated and devoted employees are the cornerstones of a school's efficacy in dealing with the different difficulties and issues thrown at it.

Teacher motivation is critical to the teaching and learning process, and however many teachers are unmotivated. This discovery should be taken seriously, and further research into the elements influencing teacher motivation is required to attain educational goals in every learning institution.

Many elements have been discovered to increase teacher motivation. Pay incentives, for example, have been shown in studies to be ineffective in increasing motivation. High levels of work discontent, stress, and burnout, according to Dai and Sternberg (2004), can have a detrimental impact on motivation and job performance. Teachers who report low levels of motivation tend to see their student's motivation levels as low, according to Gorham and Millete (1997).

According to Jackson (1997), teacher disinterest in school activities, poor attendance, unexpected absence, late arrival, lack of additional training, uncreative and unstimulating teaching, lack of interest in meetings, unhelpful attitudes when assistance is needed, the occurrence of hold-ups because deadlines are not met, resistance to contributing more than what is required of them.

In a study of 167 instructors conducted in the United States by Sylvia and Hutchinson (1985), it was discovered that teacher motivation is linked to the flexibility to try out new ideas, the assignment of suitable responsibility levels, and intrinsic job features. They argue that genuine job happiness stems from fulfilling higher-order wants rather than lower-order ones.

Teachers are undoubtedly the most crucial group of professionals for the development of our country. In her study on teacher motivation in developing countries, Michaelowa (2002) discovered that large class sizes, double-shifting, rural locations, high educational attainment, and active parental involvement were all negatively correlated with teacher job satisfaction in these countries. She also discovered that communication between teachers and school administrators had no statistically significant influence on teacher work satisfaction.

The performance of a particular school is fully dependent on the teacher's effort, and if that instructor is dissatisfied with their employment, they will not place focus on their teaching. Rodgers- Jenkinson, and Chapman (1990) discovered that the loss of experienced instructors reduces the quality of education and raises the expense of recruiting and training new teachers over time.

Research Questions

The study investigates the factors affecting the teacher's job satisfaction in public secondary schools. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. How may the satisfaction and dissatisfaction levels of teachers be described?
2. Is there a significant difference in the teachers' satisfaction levels when grouped according to sex, age, educational attainment, and academic discipline?

Literature Review

The Job Satisfaction Among Teachers

Teacher job satisfaction is an important field of research since several studies have revealed that work satisfaction impacts overall life satisfaction. The general environment significantly impacts a teacher's everyday psychological well-being. This, in turn, affects instructors' work performance (Andrew and Whitney, 1974). There is evidence that job satisfaction is linked to physical and mental health and that job satisfaction leads to total mental health improvement (Cherrington, 1989). Cherrington further claims that the frustration and despair created by a bad job pervade an individual's life and drive workers to feel miserable at work and home. Because employees who are content with their employees work harder and perform better (Beder, 1990), understanding the

drivers of job happiness can help reduce staff dissatisfaction and poor job satisfaction.

Teacher job satisfaction is a source of motivation that sustains effort in doing duties needed of effective instructors (Watson et al., 1991), such as the creation of schemes of work, daily lesson plans, thorough marking of assignments, and meticulous record-keeping to track students' development. All instructors are required to serve as disciplinarians, counselors, and role models for their students (Kenya Education Handbook, 1981). Senior instructors are also required to assist with the inspection and coaching of other teachers (The Republic of Kenya, 1998). According to Chapman (1983), good quality of professional life for the teacher correlates to improved student accomplishment.

There is evidence that pleased instructors have a positive rather than negative impact on classroom learning in the United States of America (Goodland, 1984). Teachers' wages in Kenya have been very modest compared to the private sector's financial benefits. The government has expressed worry about the significant wastage of 8 graduate instructors quitting the teaching profession (The Republic of Kenya, 1984) People join and work in organizations to meet their own requirements, according to Nzure (1999). As a result, teaching is needed to be more desirable as a career by offering as many gratifying work conditions as feasible. Work situations and job happiness appear to be relevant research topics in this setting.

Theories of Motivation and Job Satisfaction. Many people do not understand the distinction between motivation and work happiness (Okumbe, 1998). Luthans (1989) distinguished the two by defining motivation as a process that begins with a physiological or psychological deficiency or need that activates a behavior or a drive aimed at a goal or incentive, and job satisfaction as a pleasurable or positive emotional state resulting from an appraisal of one's job or job experience.

Theories of Work Motivation and Job Satisfaction. The theories of work motivation and job satisfaction seek to explain what motivates people's conduct at work. These theories focus on understanding people's wants and drives and how these needs and drives are prioritized; as a result, they are known as needs theories or cognitive theories. According to Okumbe (1998), motivation theories are primarily concerned with the kind of incentives and goals people strive for to fulfill and enhance their performance at work. This

chapter discusses three theories of work motivation: the needs Hierarchy theory, Herzberg's two-component theory, and the ERG theory.

Maslow's Needs Hierarchy Theory. Maslow's (1943) theory of human motivation is based on the premise that unsatisfied wants motivate or affect action. Requirements are placed in a descending order of significance, with an individual's wants at any level on the hierarchy emerging only when lower-level needs are pretty well supplied. A manager's use of universal needs hierarchy to inspire employees is based on the idea that pretty well-met needs do not motivate.

Maslow defined five tiers of nine needs. These are physiological needs, safety needs, love or social needs, esteem needs, and self-actualization wants. Physiological requirements are unquestionably the most fundamental in the hierarchy. Once an individual's fundamental requirements are met, they no longer motivate them. Once one's requirements are met at one level, one aspires to meet those at the next higher level. If a lower-order need is fulfilled and is jeopardized, that desire will resurface as a proponent, and attempts to satisfy all higher-order wants will be diminished (Okumbe, 1998).

Physiological requirements are the most fundamental needs in Maslow's hierarchy, and they comprise wants that must be met in order for a person to exist; these include food, water, oxygen, sleep, sex, and sensory satisfaction in the workplace, and are often met through proper income or compensation (Nzure 1999). When physiological requirements are substantially met, safety demands develop and occupy the second rung in the hierarchy of wants. These requirements include a need for security, stability, reliance, protection, and escape from fear and anxiety, as well as a desire for structure, order, and law (Cherrington, 1989).

These requirements are also met by acceptable pay or salaries, albeit Maslow does not believe that money is an effective motivation. Love or social needs are the third degrees of needs. These include connection, belongingness, acceptance, and friendship demands. The administration of an educational institution should create an environment in which employees and students may meet their love requirements. The esteem needs are the fourth degree of needs. These are requirements for self-esteem, accomplishment, and success (Maslow, 1954). Someone else must acknowledge and appreciate your accomplishment.

Self-actualization is the fifth degree of needs. This is

the most important need in Maslow's hierarchy. This is the desire to become whatever a person is capable of being. When working with and for others, it is critical to maximizing one's capabilities. While Maslow's requirements hierarchy theory is well recognized and used by actual managers, certain studies have questioned its conclusions.

Aldefer (1972) studied ten needs and strengths in cross-sectional research. The study's result did not support Maslow's hierarchy notion. Although there have been studies on motivating requirements in other groups of individuals, none have been done for secondary school teachers in Mwatate District. It is envisaged that this study of teacher work satisfaction would yield recommendations ranging from the most essential to the least significant demands of teachers in Mwatate. This data can be utilized to inspire instructors in their work.

Factors Influencing the Job Satisfaction of Teachers

Because employees who are content with their employees work harder and perform better, understanding the elements that contribute to job happiness can help reduce employee frustration and poor job satisfaction. (Beder, 1990), According to Cherrington (1989), work happiness is largely controlled by the type of incentives, the number of rewards, and the rewards expectations of employees. Several variables, according to him, contribute to the fulfilling or unrewarding quality of work. These elements include job-related traits, organizational features, and personal attributes such as age and education. Gender, age, marital status, professional qualification, job experience, subject combination, school type, remuneration, working conditions, job security, leadership, and organizational culture are all aspects to be addressed in this study.

Gender. Shepard and Hawley (1974) discovered that female instructors were less satisfied than male teachers, with the gap being greatest among individuals under 30 years old. Reyes (1990) discovered that gender was related to work satisfaction in a survey of 150 teachers in the Midwestern region of the United States. However, the survey found that women were more satisfied with their jobs and more devoted to education than males. It has been proposed that the amount of job satisfaction is related to a number of characteristics that change with sex rather than the worker's sex.

Age. In general, job happiness rises with age, with the

youngest workers reporting the lowest levels of satisfaction (Rhodes, 1990). According to research, a rise in job satisfaction with age is reliable up until the age of sixty, beyond which the data becomes less clear (Schults, 1986). According to Peter and Steers (1973), the likelihood of quitting a job decreases with age. They suggest that as workers age, they have fewer alternative employment opportunities and are less inclined to leave since longer tenure provides them with better compensation rates, longer paid vacations, and more appealing perks.

Professional Qualifications. Kimengi (1983) found that the professional variable had no effect on instructors' attitudes about teaching. The variable had a considerable effect in Okumbe's (1982) study. Graduate teachers' employment satisfaction increases with their professional-grade level.

Job Experience. Workers' job happiness and motivation rise as they gain experience. According to Reyes' (1990) research, work orientation was associated to the level of job satisfaction among instructors. Reyes came to the conclusion that teaching experience and organizational tenure were related to teacher job satisfaction. This suggested that work satisfaction rose with teaching experience.

Subject Combination. Kimengi (1983) studied secondary teachers' views about teaching and work satisfaction and discovered a substantial association between the two. A positive attitude toward teaching suggested a high level of work satisfaction, whereas a negative attitude toward teaching indicated low job satisfaction.

Remuneration. According to Kimengi's (1983) research, teachers' salaries are essential to teachers' work satisfaction. He advised that school planners evaluate the need to raise teacher compensation to keep instructors in the classroom. Kimengi's 15 (1983) study emphasized the critical functions of promotional possibilities in the teaching profession in increasing teacher job satisfaction. Several studies have found that employees prefer compensation schemes and promotion rules that they believe to be fair, clear, and in accordance with their expectations. Okumbe (1998) proposed that workers' job satisfaction is increased when they perceive equal remuneration in relation to their input. When workers believe they are not being fairly compensated, dissatisfaction comes in. Gordon (1986) said that the higher the reward, the greater the worker's job satisfaction.

The Working Conditions. Another element that has a

little impact on job satisfaction is working circumstances. According to Luthan's (1989) research, clean and pleasant environments make workers happy while doing their task, enhancing job satisfaction. Work factors related to job discontent for teachers should be discovered to modify the working environment for ongoing job happiness.

Job Security. According to Luthans (1989), job security is the sensation of being able to keep onto a job and knowing that everything will be well in the future as it has been in the past. He defines insecurity as the persistent concern that things will not endure, that one will lose what they have today. According to Flippo (1984), the demand for job security is at the top of the list of objectives for many employees and labor unions due to increasing challenges from technological development.

Leadership. Competent and fair leadership is one of the employee desires that leads to motivation and job happiness. According to Flippo (1984), competent leadership guarantees that workers' psychological and security demands are satisfied appropriately. According to Nzuve (1999), the efficacy of leaders' conduct is judged by the extent to which the manager achieves both corporate goals and employee requirements. If employees believe the supervising leader is worthless and unskilled, it becomes frustrating for them, resulting in job discontent. Flippo (1984).

Organizational Culture. Cherrington (1989) defines culture as "the collection of core values, ideas, and knowledge that members of an organization share." According to him, culture improves organizational stability by assisting members in interpreting organizational actions and events, hence minimizing work unhappiness. The goal of culture is to provide individuals a feeling of identity and to instill in them a dedication to the organization's principles and values, resulting in work satisfaction. The degree of compliance and the level of school performance is determined by culture. Scott and Meyer (1983)

Teacher Motivation

According to Ifinedo (2003), employee motivation is a complicated and difficult phrase to describe; hence, a clear description of this idea is elusive since the notion encompasses the features of the individual and the circumstance, as well as the individual's perspective of that scenario. According to Lewis, Goodman, and Fandt (1995), the vitality of an organization stems from its employees' motivation, albeit their talents are

equally as important in determining their job performance as their drive. Motivated and devoted employees may make or break an organization's success.

Employment satisfaction is an individual's level of contentment with their job. Job satisfaction is defined by Locke (1976) as a happy or good emotional state arising from an evaluation of one's employment or job experiences. A person's degree of job satisfaction is influenced by a number of things. These factors include pay, perceived fairness of the promotion system, working conditions, social ties, leadership, and the job itself. Medical practitioners' job happiness or discontent influences their relationships with coworkers, administration, and patients. Job satisfaction and motivation are thus critical to the long-term success of any educational institution worldwide.

The investigation of the link between work happiness and job performance has a tumultuous past. The Hawthorne investigations, which were undertaken in the 1930s, are often regarded with bringing to light the influence of employee attitudes on performance. Shortly after the Hawthorne trials, scholars began to question the idea that a happy worker equals a productive worker. Most previous evaluations of the literature, according to Iaffaldano and Muchinsky (1985), revealed a modest and rather inconsistent link between work satisfaction and performance. According to a 1985 analysis of the literature, the statistical association between work happiness and performance was approximate. As a result, these writers concluded that the claimed association between work happiness and performance was an unrealistic managerial fad. This study significantly influenced researchers and, in some cases, companies, with some managers and human resource practitioners concluding that the association between work happiness and performance was insignificant.

According to Organ (1988), the failure to identify a substantial association between job happiness and performance is due to the restrictive ways by which job success is frequently defined. When performance is defined to include crucial behaviors that are not often represented in performance assessments, such as organizational citizenship behaviors, the link between performance and job satisfaction increases, according to Organ. Organ's hypothesis that work happiness corresponds with organizational citizenship practices is supported by research (Organ & Ryan, 1995). Furthermore, Judge, Thoresen, Bono, and Patton (2001) discovered that when the correlations are adequately adjusted (for sampling and measurement

errors), the average correlation between work happiness and job performance is higher. Furthermore, the association between job satisfaction and performance was shown to be stronger in sophisticated (e.g., professional) employment than in less complex jobs. Thus, contrary to previous assessments, it appears that work happiness is predictive of performance, and the link is much stronger for professional employment.

Job satisfaction has been the most studied variable in organizational behavior (Spector, 1997). Job happiness differs from person to person. According to Peretomode and Whawo (1993), the higher the prestige of the work, the larger the job satisfaction. Many workers, however, are content in even the least prominent positions. They just like what they do. In any event, work satisfaction is as unique as one's sentiments or mental condition. A multitude of factors can impact job satisfaction, including the quality of one's connection with their boss, the physical setting in which they work, and the degree of fulfillment in their work. Improved job happiness, on the other hand, might occasionally reduce job performance. According to Warr (1998), professions differ in terms of how much they incorporate five basic dimensions: skill diversity, task identity, task relevance, autonomy, and task feedback. He went on to say that if jobs are designed in such a way that these core characteristics are more prevalent, three critical psychological states can occur in employees: experienced meaningfulness of work, experienced responsibility for work outcomes, and knowledge of the outcomes of work activities.

In terms of job satisfaction, there are three models. These are models of circumstance, disposition, and interaction. These three major lines of models have been widely utilized to predict employee job satisfaction in firms. According to the interactional model of job satisfaction, the fit between the individual and the environment impacts job happiness. This is known as the Person-Environment Fit method. Spokane (1985) analyzed the model literature and found that the Person-Environment Fit is connected to work satisfaction in a good way. As most recent empirical research has proven, it is realistic to anticipate personality factors to impact personal values and views (Olver and Mooradian, 2003).

Mwangi (2002) discovered that the factors affecting teachers' morale included: dissatisfaction with school authorities, low turnover and constant shortage, inadequate pay, poor career structure, lack of promotion opportunities, poor school facilities,

inadequate school disciplinary policy, attitudes and behavior of the school head and other teachers, and pupils' poor work attitude.

Factors that enhance Job Satisfaction

Identifying these elements aids the study by providing verifiable support for the issue of investigation. On the other hand, this provides a collective knowledge of what teacher work satisfaction comprises from respected scholars and authors. The information from the linked literature was disseminated to obtain precise thoughts from people who were deemed to be deceptive about the drivers of workplace happiness.

The material received from writers and other textual sources was extensively evaluated to identify censorship flaws. In his research on the causes of teacher work satisfaction, Katharina (2002) asserts that the most important component is the school environment. To be fully satisfied as a teacher at school, there must be enough facilities, good teaching materials, security, good contract terms, a nice school community, a decent wage, and positive interactions with colleagues. He also underlines that a healthy school environment includes crucial individuals who are supportive of a teacher's well-being, such as administrators, students, and parents. This builds a teacher's confidence and steadiness, and eventually results in contentment. Thus, the working environment is critical since it shapes a teacher's attitude toward work, and school administrators must constantly follow excellent practices to provide a stable and adequate atmosphere for education. Teachers must be supported if African countries are to compete in the global village of science and technology. Societal assistance to a Teacher According to Ansu (1984), social attitudes and beliefs have affected the function of teachers in most African schools. Teachers, needless to say, are considered machines in most African nations, aiming to impart information and skills to the student at any cost. A teacher is heavily criticized and accused of being ineffective when accomplishment is not attained.

Other African cultures, on the other hand, help instructors; for example, parents and other community members share the task of disciplining students. They also offer a comfortable atmosphere, such as suitable property for school development, and they financially support teachers through Parent Teacher Associations (Amanuel 2009). Nonetheless, African society has been a source of teacher discouragement in the teaching profession. Most African countries judge instructors based on their academic ability. Those that

choose schooling are seen as failures in other academic fields, such as medicine. In African civilization, education is viewed as a last resort, something to fall back on. Because of social attitudes, the education profession is seen with skepticism (Ansu 1984). Teachers are dissatisfied because certain individuals in society have bad attitudes toward education. Teachers, as mature adults, should not be repulsed by their own career, but rather value it for the fulfillments it brings to their well-being. Teachers must quietly carry on with their vocation and find delight in their work, rather than waiting to be chastised or praised for their career choice. As much as instructors dislike society's views, they must work effectively and achieve good outcomes in order to condemn those in society who neglect their profession; this improves their reputation in the profession. It should be emphasized, however, that in any life circumstance, there will be critics and supporters; not everyone will support what you do. Teachers are responsible for making sound judgements about their profession, regardless of what they hear from society. Workplace Attitudes of Employees Teachers at all educational institutions have thoughts and ideas concerning the state of their profession. They evaluate employment status in terms of prestige, subsistence, and other factors.

In most circumstances, the salary associated with the work is highly appreciated, and vice versa (Nwachukwa 2006). Most instructors acquire positive attitudes toward their jobs based on the financial outcomes they receive. Teachers will be highly motivated if their pay is satisfactory and secure. Due to a lack of proper financial support, instructors acquire negative attitudes at work, and others seek new employment or work lazily. Young, ambitious, and intelligent people, on the other hand, are not drawn to low-paying occupations. A high salary fosters stability and dedication in the teaching profession, whereas a low salary does the opposite.

According to Sekiwu (2009), instructors enter the teaching profession to meet their own needs. They anticipate that the employment will enhance their financial situation. When instructors recognize the existence of their job expectations, they become eager for their job and feel at ease about their career, receiving satisfaction from the positive attitude established as a result of a suitable school environment that matches their professional possibilities. A critical look at a teacher's needs must be applied without undermining instructors' work objectives. Teaching, in and of itself, is a sacrifice; no one can ever compensate a teacher for the amount of labor he or she does. Teachers, too, must be realistic about their

expectations, not simply to compete for big bucks, but to recognize the significance of their job and what it means to the lives of others.

As a result, teachers must first love their vocation as a contribution to society before scrambling for rewards to support their life. According to Amanuel (2009), job satisfaction of any sort may be reached first and foremost when one develops a passion and respect for the vocation he or she chooses. According to Amanuel, work satisfaction ratings are subjective. The informal social arrangement in the workplace greatly influences a worker's mindset (Appleby 2001) Individual Variables An individual has issues that contribute to job enrichment or happiness. According to Amanuel's research, personal interest in the career leads to job happiness.

According to Amanuel (2009), (Analou 1999) thinks that the amount of pleasure varies from person to person, especially when diverse persons, cultural backgrounds, organizational settings, and environmental elements are involved. Individual elements include a variety of human characteristics such as abilities, personality, and educational status. Thus, job satisfaction is composed of several values that a person consciously or unconsciously wishes to gain from a certain employment. Different people have different perspectives on satisfaction; for example, some people may consider being rewarded with a strip to be satisfying, whilst others would find happiness in remaining in one place and not being transported. According to Amanuel (2009), other individual variables that contribute to job happiness include flexibility, nice surroundings, cooperation with colleagues, job placement, and enough rest. Individual variables contributing to discontent include employment routine boredom, weariness, jealousy, excessive competitiveness, and inadequate physical surroundings (Ficker 1975, cited by Amanuel 2009).

Amanuel (2009) also cites Wallace (1982), who argues that work satisfaction is an individual's emotional and affective response to a job. The employee evaluates how well the types and amounts of awards received correlate to his or her performance. Employee motivation is complicated by job satisfaction. It features rewards and reinforcement values that boost an individual's performance spirit. It also has an impact on learning, and employees will change their conduct to fit the concepts and agreements of their jobs.

Methodology

This study employed descriptive research. Descriptive research is the type of research procedure wherein a certain phenomenon is investigated, described, and attempted to be explained. Specifically, this descriptive research employed the survey type. Good (1963) described this as collecting information that describes conditions, events, opinions, people, organizations, etc.

Population

A population or universe for a study is any group of individuals or institutions with one or more common characteristics that are of interest to the researcher (Cooper 1996). The study's respondents were 54 randomly selected teachers of Pavia National High School.

Instruments

The instrument used to gather data was a researcher-made questionnaire divided into two sections. Section A, Background Information, includes questions related to the demographic profile of the respondents. Section B, Job Satisfaction, includes the eight areas related to teacher employment: compensation and benefits, recognition, peer relationship, relationship with immediate supervisor, working environment, work volume, teaching load, and promotion.

Data Collection Procedure

The researchers obtained approval to conduct the study. A letter from the researchers to the principal of Pavia National High School was made. This allowed the researchers to get a portion of the year-end meeting. The researchers administered the instruments to the respondents who were given ample time to respond to the questions. This was to ensure a good return ratio and help respondents get a chance to seek clarification on items which proved difficult.

Data Analysis Procedure

The data gathered for this study were subjected to certain statistical treatment. Both descriptive and inferential statistics were used. Descriptive statistics used were the mean and standard deviation to identify the areas of satisfaction and dissatisfaction level of teachers. For inferential analysis, t-test for independent samples and ANOVA were used to test the significant differences in the variables. The level of significance was set at .05.

Results and Discussion

Descriptive Data Analysis

To analyze and interpret the present study's data, the researchers employed descriptive data analysis. Mean and Standard Deviation were the statistical tools employed to determine the teachers' job satisfaction levels.

Table 1. *The areas of satisfaction and dissatisfaction level of teachers*

Area Related to Teacher Employment	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Compensation and Benefits	2.63	1.03	Average
Recognition	2.46	1.09	Average
Peer Relationship	2.19	0.95	Low
Relationship with Immediate Supervisor	2.24	1.08	Average
Working Environment	2.26	1.08	Average
Work Volume	2.39	1.05	Average
Teaching Load	2.28	1.11	High
Promotion	2.48	0.99	Low

Table 1 shows the dissatisfaction of teachers. Among the eight areas, promotion and peer relations got a low dissatisfaction. It further revealed that compensation and benefits, recognition, relationship with immediate supervisor, working environment, and work volume had an average dissatisfaction. Thus, the teaching load got a high dissatisfaction.

Inferential Data Analysis

The t-test for independent samples was employed to determine whether sex could be a factor in teachers' satisfaction. Table 2 showed no significant difference in Male and Female teachers' satisfaction levels.

The male teachers had a mean score of 2.27, while female teacher respondents had 2.39. The obtained $t(52) = -3.57$, $p = .723$ indicated no significant difference.

Table 2. *The t-test result of the significant difference in the level of satisfaction when grouped according to sex*

Sex	Mean	SD	t	p
Male	2.2750	.91818	-3.57	.723
Female	2.3864	.88504		

The ANOVA was employed to determine whether educational attainment could be a factor in teachers' satisfaction. Table 3 showed no significant difference among respondents when grouped according to their educational attainment.

Table 3. *The ANOVA for the significant difference in the level of satisfaction when grouped according to educational attainment*

	Sum of Squares	Mean Square	f	p
Between Groups	.108	.054	.069	.934
Within Groups	39.362	.787		
Total	39.470	54		

The ANOVA was employed to find out whether age could be a factor in the satisfaction of teachers. Table 4 shows a significant difference among respondents when grouped according to their age. A significant difference was present between teachers aged 18-25 and those aged 36-45. Also, it was found between 36-45 and 46-55 groups.

Table 4. *The ANOVA for the significant difference in the level of satisfaction when grouped according to age*

	Sum of Squares	Mean Square	f	p
Between Groups	7.443	1.861	2.687	.042
Within Groups	33.928	.692		
Total	41.370			

The ANOVA test for independent samples was employed to determine whether the area of discipline could factor in teachers' satisfaction. Table 5 shows no significant difference among respondents when grouped according to their area of discipline or specialization.

Table 5. *The ANOVA results for the significant difference in the level of satisfaction when grouped according to the area of discipline*

	Sum of Squares	Mean Square	f	p
Between Groups	3.407	.487	.590	.761
Within Groups	37.963	.825		
Total	41.370			

Conclusion

In view of the findings, the following conclusions were drawn: most teachers are in the age bracket 26-35 years old, mostly female. 50.00% of the teachers were Bachelor's Degree. Also, 46.30% of the teachers pursued a Master's Degree while 3.70% were into Doctorate Degree. Most of the teachers were over 15 years of service. The most number of teachers are in the Science Department as it ranked first with 11 out of 54 respondents and had 20.40% of the total respondents. It was followed by English and Mathematics which tied up in the second rank. Then, the departments of Filipino, AP, and MAPEH followed the orders respectively. While with the least number of teachers came the TLE department had 1.90% of the total respondents in the study. Thus, the TLE department had the second-most number of faculty in the actual scenario.

Furthermore, promotion and peer relations got a common dissatisfaction among the eight areas. It further revealed that compensation and benefits, recognition, relationship with immediate supervisor, working environment, and work volume had a middle dissatisfaction. Thus, the teaching load got a high dissatisfaction. Also, there was a significant difference in the level of satisfaction when teachers were grouped according to age. A significant difference was present between teachers aged 18-25 and those aged 36-45. Also, it was found between 36-45 and 46-55 groups. Lastly, there was no significant difference in the level of satisfaction when teachers were grouped according to sex, age, educational attainment, academic discipline

Moreover, the findings laid the bases for the following recommendations: more training should be organized to increase the teachers' awareness and know their job satisfaction levels. This could be included in in-service training conducted for the teachers twice a school year. School administrators should give attention to teachers' teaching load for among the eight areas this had high dissatisfaction. Improvement and proper alignment of teachers' load should be given

focus.

Further, compensation and benefits, recognition, relationship with immediate supervisor, working environment, and work volume should also be on the note for improvement. Teachers should have more passion for their job and must strive to uplift the level of their satisfaction not for themselves only but for the students who are the primary reason for their existence. This study has a very limited scope of the investigation and other variables are not dealt with that will probably have a significant impact on teachers' job satisfaction. Since research outputs are not the end themselves, they can serve as a springboard to infinite quests for answers to questions and problems that beset human existence. Corollary to this, the researcher recommends a more comprehensive inquiry related to this endeavor so that investigators could be further enlightened and be benefited.

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